

Another formula for the inradius

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Here we will derive an unknown formula for the inradius of a triangle.

It is known that the intersection point of the bisecting lines of angles is the midpoint of the incircle. We view the following figure:

$$b = y + z$$

First we must determine y or z . We use both equations:

$$y + z = b \tag{1}$$

$$y \cdot \tan \frac{\gamma}{2} = z \cdot \tan \frac{\alpha}{2} \tag{2}$$

We insert equation (1) into equation (2):

$$y \cdot \tan \frac{\gamma}{2} = (b - y) \cdot \tan \frac{\alpha}{2}$$

We solve to y :

$$y = \frac{b \cdot \tan \frac{\alpha}{2}}{\tan \frac{\gamma}{2} + \tan \frac{\alpha}{2}}$$

With the second figure we see:

$$\varrho = y \cdot \tan \frac{\gamma}{2}$$

Thus:

$$\varrho = \frac{b \cdot \tan \frac{\gamma}{2} \cdot \tan \frac{\alpha}{2}}{\tan \frac{\gamma}{2} + \tan \frac{\alpha}{2}}$$

Cyclic permutation leads to:

$$\varrho = \frac{c \cdot \tan \frac{\alpha}{2} \cdot \tan \frac{\beta}{2}}{\tan \frac{\alpha}{2} + \tan \frac{\beta}{2}}$$

$$\varrho = \frac{a \cdot \tan \frac{\beta}{2} \cdot \tan \frac{\gamma}{2}}{\tan \frac{\beta}{2} + \tan \frac{\gamma}{2}}$$

These 3 formulas for the inradius cannot be found in mathematical literature.

References

- [1] Harald Schröder "Trigonometric problem cases well solved" Wissenschaft & Technik Verlag Berlin 2001